

VarBen simulation (WES)

Allele fraction type

- Reference truth
- Real variant
- Simulated variant

Batch

- A 1
- B 2
- C 3
- D 4
- E 5
- F 6

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Allele fraction (AF)

log10(depth)

Mutation

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